

π -Electron Structure and Spectra of Diazaphenanthrenes

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The resonance energies of diazaphenanthrenes with two nitrogen atoms in the adjacent rings have been predicted by means of empirical relations and compared with the Dewar resonance energy. The two sets of results are in good agreement with each other. The ground state properties and other properties such as ionisation potential, electron affinity, half-wave reduction potential and π -dipole moment have been predicted. The effect of nitrogen atom at different centres on the ground state properties has also been discussed. The $\pi^* \leftarrow \pi$ spectral transitions have also been predicted and compared with the experimental ones where available.

RECENTLY Das Gupta *et al.*^{1,2} discussed the ground state properties of a large number of azaheterocyclic systems using the semi-empirical π -electron SCF MO method of Dewar and Harget³ and $\pi^* \leftarrow \pi$ spectra using configuration interaction method. They predicted the resonance energies of azanaphthalenes, azaanthracenes and azaphenanthrenes by means of empirical relations. The results were in good agreement with the 'Dewar' resonance energy for the molecules² studied. However, they did not consider the diazaphenanthrenes with two nitrogen atoms present in the adjacent rings. In order to complete the study we report the results of our calculation on 1,5-, 2,5-, 3,5-, 4,5-, 1,6-, 2,6-, 3,6-, and 4,6-diazaphenanthrenes (Fig. 1), predicting the ground state¹ and other properties such as

Fig. 1. Phenanthrene skeleton with the numbering notation indicated.

ionisation potential, electron affinity, half-wave reduction potential and $\pi^* \leftarrow \pi$ spectra. All of these molecules are known⁴. Some of them have medicinal values and antibacterial activity. Mention may be made about 1,5-, 2,5-, 3,5-, and dimethyl derivative of 3,5-diazaphenanthrenes which have specific antimicrobial activity⁵ against different bacterial strains. Derivatives of 1,6-diazaphenanthrene has been reported to possess antimalarial activity⁶. Hence it would be worthwhile to study the molecules theoretically.

Method and parameter :

The method is well known and has been described elsewhere⁷. The procedure is the self-

consistent field approach due to Pariser and Parr⁸ and Pople⁹ modified by Dewar and Harget³ within the zero-differential overlap approximation and using semi-empirical evaluation of integrals. The resonance integral, β_{ij} , the bond length, r_{ij} , and the two-center two-electron repulsion integrals, γ_{ij} , for bonded atoms were adjusted at each iteration according to the relation,

$$r_{ij} (\text{\AA}) = a - b p_{ij} \quad (1)$$

and

$$\beta_{ij} = -K_{ij} S_{ij}^{AB} \quad (2)$$

where, p_{ij} is the π -bond order, S_{ij} is the overlap integral between $2p_{\pi}$ Slater-type orbitals at centres i and j for nuclei type A and B. The values of parameters a , b and K are given in Table 1. For non-bonded atoms β_{ij} is set equal to zero.

TABLE 1—VALUES OF PARAMETERS

Bond	K	a Å	b Å	Atoms	I_i eV	γ_{ij} eV
C-C	6.927	1.512	0.174	C	11.16	11.134
C-N	6.9612	1.448	0.178	N	14.12	12.341

The two-centre two-electron repulsion integrals, γ_{ij} were evaluated from Ohno's formula¹⁰. One-centre two-electron integrals, γ_{ii} were calculated using the relation¹¹,

$$\gamma_{ii} = I_i - A_i \quad (3)$$

where, I and A represent the valence state ionisation potential and electron affinity of atoms concerned, respectively, and the values are taken from the work of Hinze and Jaffe¹². The values of γ_{ii} and I_i are also included in Table 1.

For non-bonded centres γ_{ij} were not varied but were kept at the values calculated from the initial geometry of the molecules assumed to be planar with bond lengths equal to 1.40 Å and bond angles 120°.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF CONSTRUCTIVE AND DESTRUCTIVE INTERACTION ON CHARGE DENSITY OF N AND C

Molecules*	Charge density of N	Charge density on C at different positions					
		<i>ortho</i>	<i>meta</i>	<i>para</i>	<i>ortho-meta</i>	<i>ortho-para meta-para</i>	
Constructive Interaction							
2,5-DAP	1.42(2), 1.89(5)	0.72(1), 0.76(3)	1.14(4), 1.18(14)	0.89(13)	—	0.75(11)	—
4,5-DAP	1.41(4), 1.89(5)	0.67(6) 0.71(3), 0.66(11)	1.12(12) 1.15(2), 1.18(14)	0.85(1) 0.89(13)	—	—	—
1,6-DAP	1.41(1), 1.89(6)	0.67(6) 0.69(2), 0.69(5)	1.12(13) 1.14(3), 1.19(11)	0.84(4)	—	0.71(14)	—
3,6-DAP	1.41(3), 1.89(6)	0.89(12) 0.74(2), 0.70(4)	1.12(13) 1.14(1), 1.19(11)	0.81(14)	—	—	—
1,5-DAP	1.37(1), 1.84(5)	0.69(2), 0.83(12) 0.76(2), 0.73(6)	1.11(13) 1.09(3), 1.08(12)	0.89(4), 0.95(18)	0.97(11)	—	—
3,5-DAP	1.86(3), 1.84(5)	0.73(6) 0.81(2), 0.75(4)	1.10(1), 1.06(12)	0.94(18)	0.87(14) 0.97(11)	—	0.96(14)
2,6-DAP	1.35(2), 1.33(6)	0.73(1), 0.80(3) 0.73(5), 0.89(12)	1.09(4), 1.05(18)	—	—	—	1.08(14) 0.97(11)
4,6-DAP	1.86(4), 1.84(6)	0.75(3), 0.72(5) 0.88(12)	1.08(2), 1.06(18)	0.89(1)	0.89(11)	—	1.02(14)

* DAP = Diazaphenanthrene.

Ground state properties :

Birss and Das Gupta¹ showed that the resonance energies (RE) of the azanaphthalenes, azaanthracenes and azaphenanthrenes could be predicted by empirical relations in good agreement with the resonance energy calculated by the method of Dewar and Harget². However, in their relations, Birss and Das Gupta¹ did not study the diazaphenanthrenes where the two nitrogen atoms are present in adjacent rings. In the present formula for RE, the interaction has been included modifying the empirical relation represented as

$$RE = 2.125 + 0.025 N + 0.258 (C_R - D_R) + 0.061 (C_X - D_X) + 0.036 (C_{XX} - D_{XX}) \quad (4)$$

where, N is the number of nitrogen atoms in the compound, C_R and D_R are the number of constructive and destructive interactions between nitrogen atoms in the same ring, C_X and D_X the number of such interactions in the neighbouring rings and C_{XX} and D_{XX} refer the interactions between nitrogens in the outermost rings. These interactions have been explained by Birss and Das Gupta¹ in terms of charge density alteration induced by introduction of a nitrogen atoms into a benzene ring. The charge densities on *meta* position are enhanced and those on *ortho* and *para* positions are depressed in comparison with the phenanthrene value. However, the depression on the *ortho* position is greater than at the *para* position. It seems that nitrogen atoms act as electron-withdrawing group. The effect of enhancement and depression for two nitrogen atoms may act simultaneously in some cases. As a result, the increase of charge density will be more on a carbon centre *meta* to two nitrogen atoms and the opposite effect will be seen in case of centres *ortho* or *para* to two nitrogen atoms. However, constructive and destructive interactions not only have an effect on the charge density of *ortho*, *meta* and *para* carbon atoms, but

on nitrogen atoms as well. In case of constructive interaction, the effect of enhancement or depression on the charge density of nitrogen atoms is more than in the case of destructive interaction. This is evident from Table 2 which contains the charge density of carbons and nitrogens in the substituted rings of phenanthrene. Table 3 contains the values of resonance energies predicted by relation (4) and those calculated by the method of Dewar and Harget along with the value of heat of atomisation ΔH_a , and π -bond energy $E_{\pi b}$. It is evident from the Table 3 that the two sets of values of RE are in good agreement with each other.

 TABLE 3—HEAT OF ATOMISATION (ΔH_a), RESONANCE ENERGY (RE), π -BOND ENERGY ($E_{\pi b}$) AND π -DIPOLE MOMENT (μ)

Molecule*	ΔH_a eV	$E_{\pi b}$ eV	Resonance energy (eV)		μ (D)
			RE ^b	RE ^c	
1,5-DAP	118.625	20.842	2.116	2.114	1.12
2,5-DAP	118.749	20.895	2.240	2.236	3.00
3,5-DAP	118.623	20.837	2.114	2.114	3.00
4,5-DAP	118.740	20.879	2.231	2.236	2.84
1,6-DAP	118.740	20.886	2.231	2.236	2.63
2,6-DAP	118.593	20.806	2.034	2.114	0.76
3,6-DAP	118.733	20.882	2.224	2.236	0.76
4,6-DAP	118.803	20.827	2.095	2.114	2.16

*DAP = Diazaphenanthrene. ^bCalculated using the formula of Dewar and Harget. ^cCalculated using the empirical relation (Eq. 4)

The constructive-destructive interference concept also serves as a guide to the deviation of bond lengths from the phenanthrene values. The bond length behaviour of these molecules is similar to that of analogous azaanthracenes¹. In the unsubstituted ring, the bond length differs from the phenanthrene value by 0.001 Å in case of destructive interaction and in case of constructive interaction it differs by 0.002–0.003 Å. When constructive

interaction occurs the fused bond length between the substituted rings is 0.007 to 0.009 Å longer than the corresponding bond length of phenanthrene, while destructive interference causes a shortening of bond length by 0.001 to 0.003 Å. However, in these molecules the lengthening of bond is larger than in the corresponding diazaanthracenes¹. But shortening of bond is the same as that of similar diazaanthracenes¹. The C—C bond lengths of the substituted rings differ from those of phenanthrenes by 0.006 Å at most.

Ionisation potential, electron affinity and π-dipole-moment :

According to Koopmans' theorem¹³ the ionisation potential (IP) can be approximated by the highest occupied orbital energy, e_1 . But predicted value of IP is 1 or 2 eV higher than the true value. In case of electron affinity (EA) it can also be approximated by the lowest unoccupied orbital energy, e_j . Here too the theoretical value of EA differs from the true value by 1 or 2 eV. Hence a correction term should be added in both the cases of IP and EA. The following relations between IP and e_1 and EA and e_j are in common use in the literature,

$$IP = -(e_1 + C) \quad (5)$$

and

$$EA = -(e_j + D) \quad (6)$$

where, C and D are correction terms. As suggested by Birss and Das Gupta¹, the values of C is 1.88 eV. It has been seen that ionisation potential of a large number of benzenoid and azaheterocyclic systems could be predicted well using the above value of correction term. The value of D is 1.13, being the difference between the lowest unoccupied orbital energy and the electrons affinity of phenanthrene. The predicted value of IP and EA are presented in Table 4, which also contains the calculated values

TABLE 4—IONISATION POTENTIAL (IP), ELECTRON AFFINITY (EA) AND HALF-WAVE REDUCTION POTENTIAL ($E_{1/2}$)

Molecule*	IP eV	EA eV	$-E_{1/2}$ V
1,5-DAP	7.88	0.90	+1.85
2,5-DAP	8.12	0.89	+1.78
3,5-DAP	7.96	0.77	+1.88
4,5-DAP	7.99	0.89	+1.78
1,6-DAP	8.07	0.76	+1.89
2,6-DAP	8.01	1.08	+1.62
3,6-DAP	8.09	0.67	+1.96
4,6-DAP	8.11	0.96	+1.72

* DAP= Diazaphenanthrene.

of $E_{1/2}$, the half-wave reduction potential from the relation proposed by Birss and Das Gupta¹,

$$E_{1/2} = -0.833 e_j - 3.46 \quad (7)$$

The theoretical π-dipolemoment calculated by us is included in Table 3 (experimental values are not presently available).

π←π spectra :*

π*←π spectra have been studied for these diazaphenanthrenes using configuration interaction, CI. Instead of using Ohno's formula for two-centre two-electron repulsion integrals, the formula of Mataga and Nishimoto¹⁴ was used. Because in the context of configuration interaction the use of Mataga and Nishimoto formula for γ_{11} , π*←π spectral transitions of a large number of conjugated systems^{2,15} can be predicted with reasonably good accuracy. The value of K for β_{C-C} used in the CI procedure is 9.1846 eV (Ref. 2) instead of 6.927 eV and for β_{C-N} it is 6.9612 eV, the same as used in the SCF procedure. With this slight modification we utilised the SCF procedure of Dewar and Harget to generate the final vectors, β-integrals and γ-integrals to be used in the CI procedure where all the configurations arising from one-electron excitations involving orbitals are obtained in a prior self-consistent field calculation.

As in the case of other diazaphenanthrenes², the theoretical spectral transitions of these molecules can be grouped into distinct regions in which there

TABLE 5—π*←π SPECTRAL TRANSITIONS, ΔE(eV) AND OSCILLATOR STRENGTH (f)^a

Molecule ^b	Experimental		Present work		Other work	
	ΔE	log ε	ΔE	f	ΔE	f
1,5-DAP	3.63 ^c		3.50	0.24	3.56 ^e	
	4.26 ^c		4.11	0.18	4.19 ^e	
	4.58 ^c		4.49	0.18	4.57 ^e	
	5.20 ^d	4.70	5.11	0.45		
			5.51	0.29		
σ			(0.111)			
1,6-DAP	3.62 ^c		3.55	0.04	3.67 ^e	
	4.09 ^c		3.99	0.15	4.18 ^e	
			4.41	0.50		
			4.60	0.47		
			4.87	0.16		
		5.05	0.52			
σ			5.69	0.02		
			(0.083)		(0.045)	
4,6-DAP ^e	3.59	3.31	3.51	0.77		
	3.63 ^c				3.60 ^e	
	3.78	3.27	3.86	0.37		
	4.0 ^c				3.91 ^e	
			4.50	4.32	4.58	0.15
		4.95	4.50	5.02	0.93	
		5.44	4.81	5.51	0.09	
		5.83	4.68	5.82	0.41	
σ			(0.07)			
2,5-DAP			3.57	0.56		
			4.02	0.34		
			4.68	0.17		
	5.08 ^d	4.68	5.03	0.92		
			5.20	0.71		
		5.57	0.19			
3,5-DAP			3.59	0.07		
			4.05	0.15		
			4.40	0.29		
			4.83	0.91		
	5.08 ^d	4.67	5.09	0.78		
		5.49	0.05			
		5.79	0.10			

^aRef. 16. ^bDAP= Diazaphenanthrene. ^cRef. 17. ^dRef. 5. ^eRef. 18. σ=Standard deviation.

TABLE 6— $\pi^* \leftarrow \pi$ SPECTRAL TRANSITIONS, ΔE (eV), AND OSCILLATOR STRENGTH (f)^a, OF DIAZAPHENANTHRENE (DAP)

Molecule ^b	Present work		Molecule	Present work		Molecule	Present work	
	ΔE	f		ΔE	f		ΔE	f
4,5-DAP ^c	3.58	0.22	2,6-DAP ^c	3.40	0.19	3,6-DAP ^c	3.57	0.04
	4.04	0.31		3.87	0.26		4.04	0.12
	4.52	0.01		4.52	0.04		4.69	0.66
	4.96	0.58		4.90	0.36		4.78	1.12
	5.17	0.67		5.20	1.11		5.10	0.33
	5.52	0.25		5.52	0.41		5.59	0.09
6.06	0.25	5.80	0.21	5.84	0.04			

^aRef. 16. ^bDAP=Diazaphenanthrene. ^cExperimental values not available in literature.

are significant absorptions. These regions are 3.5–4.2, 4.4–4.7, 4.8–5.4 and > 5.5 eV. The results of our calculations are presented in Table 5. For comparison, the experimental and other available theoretical results are included in Table 5. Among these molecules, complete experimental information is available only for 1,5- and 4,6-diazaphenanthrenes. It is clear that our results (Table 5) are in good agreement with the experimental transitions of 1,5- and 4,6-diazaphenanthrenes and better than the theoretical work of Lewenowicz *et al.*¹⁷ who, however, did not report any calculated transition corresponding to 5.20 eV of the former molecule and reported only two transitions of the latter. Two experimental transitions of 1,6-diazaphenanthrene are available in the literature¹⁷. The agreement between the present work and the experimental transitions is good and comparable with that of others¹⁷. For 2,5- and 3,5-diazaphenanthrenes, $\lambda_{\max}$ values at 5.03 and 5.08 eV, respectively, are reported in the literature⁶. If the value of oscillator strengths corresponds qualitatively to intensity, then the calculated transitions at 5.03 and 5.09 eV with very high value of oscillator strength are in very good agreement with the value of $\lambda_{\max}$ of 2,5- and 3,5-diazaphenanthrenes. Standard deviation for 1,5-, 1,6- and 4,6-diazaphenanthrene has been included in the Table 5. For other molecules there is no experimental spectral transitions available in the literature and the theoretical values are included in Table 6.

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